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PULI Program Tec de Monterrey-Chiba University 2023: Co-designing a cross cultural educational program for social good

Programa PULI Tec de Monterrey-Chiba: Co-diseño de programa educativo transcultural dirigido por el diseño

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Resumen:

Como parte del Programa PULI (Post Urban Living Innovation) de la Universidad de Chiba en Japón, se propone un modelo educativo para la innovación social formado por bucles iterativos en torno al proceso de diseño, con el objetivo principal de desarrollar soluciones para problemas locales. El modelo propone una etapa inicial donde estudiantes universitarios, profesores e investigadores de diferentes países analizan y definen un proyecto para mejorar una comunidad local en Monterrey, México "Campana Altamira". Como resultado de la etapa inicial del proceso se propone "Semillas del futuro", un programa educativo centrado en abordar dos problemas principales de la comunidad: la gestión de desechos y la accesibilidad a la educación. El programa propuesto se basa en prácticas sostenibles como el upcycling, el reciclaje y las técnicas de micro manufactura dirigidas a niños para fomentar el ingenio y la creatividad utilizando la tecnología. Uno de los objetivos es crear un programa autosuficiente a largo plazo por lo que se propone una estructura modular en la que las instituciones implicadas se encargan de dirigir el proceso e involucrar gradualmente a los miembros de la comunidad facilitando la co-creación hasta que puedan seguir el proceso de diseño de forma autónoma replicando el modelo y proponiendo soluciones, productos y servicios para su propia comunidad.

Abstract:

As part of PULI (Post Urban Living Innovation) Program from Chiba University in Japan, an educational model for social innovation is proposed in order to create iterative educational loops around the design process, with the main objective of developing solutions for local problems. The model proposes an initial stage where university students, professors and researchers from different countries analyze and define a project to improve a local community in Monterrey, Mexico "Campana Altamira". As a result of the initial stage of the design process "Semillas del futuro" was proposed as an educational program focused on tackling two main problems in the community: waste management and education accessibility. The proposed program is rooted in sustainable practices like upcycling, recycling and micromanufacturing techniques targeted to children to encourage resourcefulness and creativity using technology. One of the goals is to create a self-sufficient program capable of continuing in the long term, the model proposes a modular structure where Institutions involved are intended to run the process and gradually involve community members as a co-creation partners until they can be able to follow the design process autonomously replicating the model and proposing solutions, products and services for their own community.

Palabras clave: Educación para el futuro, educación basada en el diseño, diseño para el bien social

Keywords: Future education, design-led education, design for social good

1. Introduction:

In pursuit of an inclusive and sustainable future, equitable access to education and technological literacy has become vitally important. However, underprivileged communities face challenges in accessing technologies and educational opportunities. To address this issue and empower children from marginalized backgrounds, a transformative social project has been proposed with the aim of introducing the design process and technology from an early age. The project "Semillas del futuro" was a result of following a design process during two international workshops, where participants from Tecnológico de Monterrey and Chiba University, analyzed the local environment in Monterrey, Mexico, and define issues to solve in a community near to Tecnológico de Monterrey. This project aims to empower children in local Mexican communities to use technology, create and produce tangible solutions, and engage in sustainable practices such as upcycling and recycling. At the heart of this initiative is a multidimensional approach that encompasses technology education and micromanufacturing. By weaving these elements, the project seeks to create a holistic learning experience that fosters creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among children. By nurturing their innate curiosity and imagination, the project aims to foster a passion for learning and pave the way for them to continue their studies.

2. Development

This project emerged as a collaboration between Chiba University, Japan and Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico under the initiative of designing new solutions to improve Mexican development opportunities. PULI for its acronym Post Urban Living Innovation was started by Chiba University in 2015 where several Mexican universities collaborated, including Tec de Monterrey and UDEM under the name of PULI 001 Design Against Crime (Chacon, Juan Carlos et al. 2018). According to the PULI 2023 program scheme, collaboration is planned in a period of three to five years with the new objective of developing a new educational system for the future. Research activities are carried out to detect opportunities and develop strategies on educational issues for the future, using technology. This PULI program proposes three fundamental stages for its development. The first stage is dedicated to research, conceptualization and proposal, the second stage dedicated to the prototyping of the previously selected

solutions and the third stage dedicated to the evaluation and testing of the prototypes. This publication reports the activities and findings of the first phase of the program during the first year of the project. During the first session of the workshop, students defined and analyzed an area near the Tec de Monterrey campus "Campana Altamira" that currently does not belong to the Tec District project, however it is an area that presents big challenges and opportunities for social innovation.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Campana Altamira is an area of Monterrey, Mexico that has been dealing with a number of social challenges that significantly affect the quality of life and development opportunities of its inhabitants, especially the young population. Situated in an environment of vibrant culture and development possibilities, this region faces multiple issues that demand attention and innovative solutions. The purpose of this study is to shed light on the intricate community, with special attention to the development and education of its children. The Campana Altamira area has 19,543 inhabitants (Gaceta Municipal del Gobierno de Nuevo León, 2021) where 33.87% of their population is under 18 years old, equivalent to 6,620 inhabitants. However, 10% of children and young inhabitants between 5 and 18 years old have dropped out of school in the last 3 years and 2.88% of its population is illiterate. In addition to these demographic data, this area has very few educational facilities. There is only one kindergarten and one elementary school that is overpopulated. Besides these problems of accessibility to education, there are other conditions that have a high impact on the current situation, from its location in a mountainous area, its social composition as well as the poor accessibility to basic public services. Currently, the community is at great risk and vulnerability to different natural disasters and health problems, due to the topographical conditions and the construction of unregulated housing, together with the lack of basic services such as water and drainage, lighting and electricity, as well as waste and garbage treatment. As part of the social innovation design process, the garbage treatment was defined as one of the problems that can be tackled to improve the living conditions of the inhabitants, since there are a large number of informal garbage dumps because public services are not capable of reaching the top of the mountain. These dumps cause various problems such as air pollution, soil contamination, infestation of rats

and other dangerous species and insecurity perception. This project considers the lack of educational systems and waste management problems as an opportunity to improve the living conditions of the community of Campana Altamira in Monterrey Mexico. As a reference, previous social projects such as waste management in Liliba village in Kupang City found a correlation between education and community participation, both of which are absolutely essential in the implementation of community waste management. (Tarigan, Lidia H. 2020) However, just organizing the community for waste management may not be enough for a long-term sustainable project, as education is a key part of proposing new solutions to improve processes and the environment. According to the study “Students’ Ability to Pose a Problem: The Case of Waste” (Ifigenia Iliopoulou, 2019) students who had knowledge of reusing, recycling and sustainable techniques were able to propose new solutions to this complex problem related not only to discarding the waste but also to other issues such as consumption, concluding that through education we can impact the way in which we address a complex problem considering other several implications.

2.2 Description of the innovation

In the pursuit of fostering socially conscious, innovative, and proactive individuals, we propose an educational model centered around the design process for social innovation where the goal is to make this project a self-

sufficient program capable of being continued in the long term.

The proposed educational model is grounded in a structured iterative design process, divided into three distinct stages: 1. Research, and Conceptualization, 2. Prototyping and 3. Testing. This process forms the core of the model, guiding participants through an iterative and organic journey of problem-solving and innovation. Also, The proposed educational model consists of a continuous learning loop that extends beyond the initial stage of the design process. The first iteration of the three-stage program can be considered the initial loop, involving university students, professors, and researchers from Tec de Monterrey and Chiba University, where they need to propose and develop solutions for a local social problem following the design process and gradually including community members, initiating them on the final stages of the design process (Testing stage). However, in order to succeed in the long term, this process or loop should be repeated several times until the community members join a co-designing process organically, getting involved also in the first stages of the process (Research, conceptualization and prototyping). Finally, after several loops and iterations, we intend that those community members will be able to replicate the loop by following the design process autonomously and start proposing and developing solutions for their own local social problems.

Figure 1. Proposal of Iterative educational model for social innovation based on the design process

Note. The Iterative Design process should be repeated several times until the community members get involved and replicate the model.

2.3 Innovation implementation process

Following the initial loop, during the stage 1. Research and Conceptualization during the Mexico workshop we used the Design Thinking method as a starting point, as well as ethnographic research activities integrating Mexican and Japanese students in the identification of a problem in Mexico, empathy maps were developed, user persona creation, brainstorming, a first value proposition for the project was developed and the basis of the project was built based on the preliminary research. The Design Thinking method was practical to use despite the different nationalities and cultural backgrounds of the participants. During the workshop in Japan, ethnographic activities were also carried out to analyze the activities that take place in this country regarding education within the communities, visits were made to science museums and educational structures within the community to obtain information regarding the programs, initiatives, technologies, materials and infrastructure.

Figure 3. Workshop in Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico 2023.

Note. Tecnológico de Monterrey and Chiba University students during the research and conceptualization stage with Víctor José González Fregoso, Stakeholder of Campana Altamira social project.

Figure 2. Proposed design process to be followed over the next 2 years

Note. Tec de Monterrey and Chiba University participants will run the process until stage 3. where community members will join the project during the testing stage.

Figure 4. Discussion during the research and conceptualization stage

Note. Tecnológico de Monterrey and Chiba University students during the research and conceptualization stage during Workshop

As a result of the first stage of “Research and Conceptualization”, a set of parameters were defined with the objective of improving the local area of Campana Altamira:

- **The Problem:** The defined problems to tackle were education and waste management.
- **The users:** Elementary school students. After

analyzing the current situation of education in the community, data showed a high dropout rate after elementary school and junior highschool, making it a crucial stage to promote a continuous education and reinforce skills to support the generation of socially conscious and technologically literate young individuals.

- **Value Proposition:** A hands-on educational project called “Semillas del futuro” to promote Design skills from early-ages (Problem-Solving, Communication, Creativity, Collaboration and Critical Thinking) through the use of technology with a micro manufacturing approach and promoting sustainable practices like upcycling, recycling and managing waste.

- **Key Activities:**

- A. Sustainability

Due to the community’s waste management problems, an approach focused on sustainable education and reuse of materials is essential for this project. The project Semillas del futuro seeks to utilize waste and wasteland as valuable resources, with a particular focus on adopting the Precious Plastic method with the objective of converting waste into new materials that following a design process allow them to build solutions for their environment like objects, new systems or furniture, etc.

- B. Bottom-up innovation approach

Embracing a bottom-up innovation approach, Semillas del Futuro empowers the community of Campana Altamira to actively participate in decision-making and problem-solving processes. Inspired by interconnected initiatives referred to as ‘translocal networks’, the project taps into (trans)national grassroots networks, tailoring the approaches to suit the distinct local cultural context, leveraging the Precious Plastic method, a bottom-up approach is employed to address the waste problem in the region (Loorbach et al., 2020, as cited in Spekkink, W. R., 2020). Ethnographic approach should be adopted to deeply understand the social-cultural values, waste generation patterns, and traditional waste management practices.

- C. Micro manufacturing using technological resources

A key activity proposed for this project is the promotion of a micro-manufacturing system that utilizes easily reproducible technology and can be capable to align effectively with local needs and aspirations providing unique opportunities for hands-on learning and skill

development. By employing open-source and easily accessible technology, the community can be self-reliant in the manufacturing process, reducing dependency on institution entities. This is also to address the problem that leads to the temporary closing of Fablab la Campana (González-Nieto, N.A., 2020), as the program is too reliant on time provided by scholars and administrative staff from Tec de Monterrey.

- D. Considering cultural background

Considering the cultural background when implementing a project involves understanding the specific values, practices, and needs of the community to ensure that the initiatives resonate and align effectively with the local context. This approach is particularly important when introducing technology as part of a solution. By utilizing technology that can be assembled by themselves, appropriated, recreated and holds ‘no value’ to steal, the focus shifts from imposing external solutions onto the community to empowering them to take ownership of the technological aspects of the project. Also promotes problem-solving and troubleshooting skills, essential for making the machine work effectively offering the challenge of understanding and operating a local machine instills a sense of curiosity, driving them to explore different aspects of technology, from mechanics to programming.

- E. Accessibility and infrastructure

Accessibility is a cornerstone of the project’s design, ensuring that knowledge and resources are readily available to the community. By focusing on proximity, the project establishes a physical modular space near the area, making it convenient for residents to access and participate, and also including some digital materials distributed through open platforms. The use of movable spaces for experimentation, learning, and production further enhances accessibility, as these spaces can be set up flexibly in areas easily reachable by the community members. The project’s emphasis on accessibility extends beyond the physical aspect to encompass knowledge sharing and learning opportunities. By promoting open knowledge dissemination, the project creates an environment where information and expertise are freely shared.

Finally, Semillas del Futuro, not only promotes sustainability but also fosters a sense of ownership and pride among the residents, as they actively engage in the manufacturing processes that contribute to waste reduction and environmental preservation. As this innovative model

is further refined and replicated, it holds the potential to inspire similar sustainable initiatives across latin america, contributing to a cleaner, greener and more self-reliant future.

2.4 Evaluation of results

In this initial stage the results obtained so far have been the following: identify different cultural models between Mexico and Japan to carry out educational activities towards the future, detect a real problem within the Campana Altamira community in Monterrey Mexico, analysis of systems and technologies of circular economy that can be part of the project, design and development of the first conceptual proposal to intervene in the community “Semillas del futuro” project, and also the construction of a first physical prototype of a plastic grinder machine builded by students during the workshop in Japan to test the feasibility of the design proposal, design of a strategy to iterate and implement the educational model in the community.

Note. Proposal developed by students during PULI workshop in Chiba University, Japan.

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, this new educational system proposes the use of the iterative design process, including collaborative practices, a mix of participants with different cultural and social backgrounds, proposes research-based problem solving, has a social and practical approach, and proposes that cyclical repetition is a key factor to establish a working framework that participants will be able to implement in their daily lives.

By incorporating design thinking into education, we foster a culture of problem-solving and critical thinking, equipping individuals with the skills needed to address real-world challenges. Furthermore, embracing a bottom-up approach, where solutions and proposals arise from students and community members, promotes inclusivity and ownership, as they become active participants in shaping their own solutions. By starting the initial loop with university students, professors, and researchers and gradually inviting community members to participate, we foster collaboration and knowledge exchange, ultimately empowering the community to replicate the problem-solving skills independently. Through this inclusive and participatory process, we envision creating a meaningful and lasting impact on society, fostering innovation, empowerment, and positive change within our communities.

Figure 5. Workshop in Chiba University, Japan 2023.

Note. Students developing the first prototypes of plastic recycling machines

Figure 6. Minimum Viable Prototypes of DIY machines for plastic recycling

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